

Vidyajyoti

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Editorial

HR VALUES FOR A FRUITFUL MINISTRY

“**W**e are not called to be successful; we are called to be fruitful.” Although Mother Teresa’s famous quote speaks about *faithfulness*, we can also say the same about *fruitfulness* because the word of God constantly invites us to be fruitful (Mt 3:8-10; 7:17-19; 21:19; Mk 4:20; Lk 13:6-9; Jn 12:24; 15:2-16; Rom 7:4; Gal 5:22). The way to fruitfulness is organic and kenotic. It consists in falling to the ground like a grain of wheat, dying to oneself, and thus becoming abundantly fruitful. The biblical fruitfulness is not quantitative but qualitative, not breadth oriented but depth seeking. This fruitfulness is God’s enterprise, in which we are co-workers. Just as every *successful* business enterprise makes use of its Human Resource (HR) department, for the *fruitful* enterprise of God, the Kingdom of God, highly effective HR values are required.

1. HR DEPARTMENT FOR A SUCCESSFUL BUSINESS AND HR VALUES FOR A FRUITFUL MINISTRY

HR Department is an essential part of commercial enterprises. This department’s personnel perform various functions such as (i) recruitment, (ii) training, (iii) employer-employee

relations, (iv) maintaining company culture, (v) managing employee benefits, (vi) creating a safe working environment, (vii) handling disciplinary actions, etc. In some way, Church leaders – clergy, religious, and lay – play a role similar to HR personnel. Just as HR managers act as a link between employer and employee, Church leaders are supposed to be a link between God and people. Just as highly effective HR professionals in business enterprises ensure success of their respective businesses, effective Church leaders ensure fruitfulness of the Kingdom of God.

Each organization insists on its vision, mission, and core values. In order to perform their ministerial functions fruitfully and bear much fruit for the Kingdom of God, Church leaders need to inculcate certain HR values. Interestingly, several ecclesial HR values actually begin with the letters H and R. With the letter H, we get myriad of values such as humility, hope, happiness, hard work, honesty, humanity, heroism, helpfulness, harmony, humour, etc. In the same way, with the letter R, we get abundant of values such as reliability, resilience, resourcefulness, respect, righteousness, radiance, rigour, responsibility, renewal, receptivity, etc. Each of these values plays an important role in the fruitfulness of one's ministry. However, we will try to focus only on 2Hs and 2Rs. 2Hs are Holiness and Hospitality, and 2Rs are Repentance and Reconciliation. By imbibing these core ecclesial HR values, Church leaders can become effective co-workers in the vineyard of the Lord.

2. 2Hs: HOLINESS AND HOSPITALITY

2.1 Holiness: The Vision of Isaiah in Isa 6:1-8

The Dogmatic Constitution *Lumen Gentium* of the Second Vatican Council invites not only priests and religious but all Christians to a life of holiness (LG 39). St. Paul in his epistles repeatedly refers to all Christians who are sanctified in Christ Jesus as saints (Rom 1:7; 1 Cor 1:2; 2 Cor 1:1; Eph 1:1; Phil 1:1; Col 1:2; Philem 1:5). This holiness entails

three stages: (i) coming into God's holy presence, (ii) humbly getting cleansed from our sinfulness, and (iii) being sent into the world for the transformation of others in the image and likeness of God's holiness. These three stages of holiness are vividly depicted in the spectacular vision of Prophet Isaiah in the Temple of Jerusalem.

(i) *Entering into the Holy Presence*: The narration of the call of Isaiah is of epic proportion. In a few verses, the Prophet expresses his mystical encounter with the tremendous and fascinating mystery. "Holy, holy, holy is the LORD of hosts; the whole earth is full of his glory" (Isa 6:3). God is referred to as "holy, holy, holy" in the song of the seraphim (cf. Rev 4:8). Triple holy signifies superlative holiness and the climax of sacredness. A somewhat similar sentiment is expressed in the first petition: "hallowed be Thy name" in the prayer "Our Father." When we recite this petition, like Isaiah, we enter into the holy presence of the Lord. This petition refers to chastity, which is not only for priests and religious but also for all the faithful according to their state of life. Through chastity, which is single-minded loving devotion, believers bear testimony to the holiness of God and express their aspiration for holiness. Holiness is our life's project because the book of Leviticus repeatedly exhorts us: "You are to be holy to me because I, the Lord, am holy" (Lev 20:26; 19:2; 20:7; 11:44).

(ii) *Humbly getting cleansed from our impurities*: In the presence of the supreme holiness of God, Isaiah realizes his sinfulness and his utter unworthiness. He exclaims: "Woe is me! I am lost, for I am a man of unclean lips, and I live among a people of unclean lips" (Isa 6:5). Encounter with the utter holiness of God evokes a response of humility on our part. We find Job expressing a similar sentiment after he encounters the Lord in the whirlwind (Job 42:5). When Peter realizes the true nature of Jesus after the miraculous catch of fish, he also gives a somewhat similar response (Lk 5:8).

We humans in our sinfulness and uncleanness cannot stand in the holy presence of God. We need cleansing, purging, purification. The transition from sinfulness to holiness is a deeply humbling, painful, and purgative process. Listening to the humble response of Isaiah, one of the seraphim, one burning with the love and holiness of God, touches the mouth of Isaiah with the burning coal from the altar and purifies him.

(iii) *Being sent into the world for its transformation:* After being purified, and after his heart starts burning with the loving holiness of God like that of Seraphim, Prophet Isaiah is able to listen to the call of God and respond wholeheartedly. The Lord says, “Whom shall I send, and who will go for us?” And Isaiah immediately answers: “Here am I; send me!” (Isa 6:8). The mission of God does not call for *fuga mundi*, but for incarnation, insertion in the world. There is a pharisaic separatist tendency among certain believers to keep themselves aloof, to isolate themselves from others to maintain their purity. However, the way to holiness is the way of incarnation, the way of immersion in the negative situations of the world and transforming the negativity through self-emptying love. Biblical holiness is measured not only by one’s nearness to God through prayer and worship, but through one’s care and concern towards one’s neighbour. This holiness is practical holiness, manifested in ethical living, which entails loving our neighbours as ourselves (Lev 19:18) and culminates in loving one another as Jesus has loved us (Jn 15:12).

2.2 Hospitality: Standing and Serving like Abraham; Sitting and Listening like Mary of Bethany

Chevalier Louis de Jaucourt describes hospitality in the *Encyclopédie* as the virtue of a great soul that cares for the whole universe through the ties of humanity. Hospitality is at the heart of oriental spirituality and the Bible is full of stories of hospitality. For the semi-nomadic tribes of Israel

in the Old Testament and for the itinerant preachers in the New Testament giving and receiving hospitality entailed a key virtue. Abraham and Mary of Bethany with their large-hearted service have become models of hospitality for us.

(i) *Standing and Serving like Abraham*: “Abraham stood by them under the tree while they ate” (Gen 18:8). Abraham was extremely generous, respectful, and hospitable towards three guests who came to his tent on a hot day. Taking inspiration from this episode, Hebrews 13:2 exhorts us: “Be not forgetful to show hospitality to strangers: for thereby some have entertained angels unawares.” The Greek word used in this verse is *philo-xenia*. In our xenophobic world, where “*xenos*” (stranger or foreigner) is feared, treated with suspicion, and is demonized and hated, we need a strong wave of “*philo-xenia*,” love of strangers and foreigners. This was symbolically demonstrated by Pope Francis by inaugurating a 20-foot tall bronze and clay sculpture by the Canadian artist Timothy Schmalz, titled “Angels Unawares” on 29 September 2019, on the 105th World Day of Migrants and Refugees, in St. Peter’s Square. Before blessing it, the Pope Francis explained: “The work depicts a group of migrants from various cultures and different historical periods. I wanted it here in St. Peter’s Square, so that it would remind everyone of the evangelical challenge of welcoming.”

(ii) *Sitting and Listening like Mary of Bethany*: As an itinerant preacher, Jesus enjoyed the hospitality of people who invited him to dine with them. Jesus was on the way to Jerusalem, where he would be crucified. On the way, he wished to relax and spend some quality time with his friends Martha, Mary, and Lazarus. Martha welcomed Jesus and prepared a meal for him, and “Mary... sat at the Lord’s feet and listened to what he was saying” (Lk 10:39). The mistake of Martha was not being busy with cooking, but failing to realize at that given moment what was more important for Jesus. Hospitality is more about understanding the needs of

the guest, than doing what we would like to do. Mary chose the better part because she was able to discern, what was important for Jesus at that particular point of time.

3. 2Rs: REPENTANCE AND RECONCILIATION

3.1 Repentance: Following the Nineveh Model

The Bible considers repentance as a key prerequisite for salvation. In the Old Testament, repentance is expressed by the Hebrew word “*shub*” (literally “return”), which is considered as the most important concept in the Prophetic literature. In the New Testament, Greek word “*metanoia*” (literally “change of mind”) is given pride of place in the preaching of John the Baptist and subsequently in the preaching of Jesus and his disciples. Seven psalms (Pss 6, 32, 38, 51, 102, 130, and 143) are considered as the Penitential Psalms, where the Psalmist brings his broken and contrite heart before God and pleads for his mercy. In the book of Jonah, the reluctant prophet, we find a fitting model of repentance.

Jonah’s proclamation received a wholehearted response from the people of Nineveh. In order to manifest their repentance, they carried out four actions: they fasted, they wore sackcloth, they prayed by crying out to God for mercy, and they left their evil ways. It was the ordinary people, who first listened, believed, and took decision to repent. Winds of change started blowing from the grassroots. They were further promoted by the proclamation of repentance made by the King of Nineveh. Broken and contrite hearts have an immense power, even the power to change the mind of God.

To the Israelites asking for signs, Jesus presents the Ninevites, as a model of repentance (Lk 11:29-32). In the Gospel of Matthew, the sign of Jonah stands for the resurrection, but in the Gospel of Luke, it stands for repentance. Miracles, signs, and wonders do not necessarily increase our faith. What is needed is repentance because only genuine repentance can lift us into the heart of God.

We are constantly called for repentance. Constant *metanoia*, constant change of mind, is not a sign of instability or uncertainty. It is rather a radical openness, an ability to keep one's mind open to perceive the promptings of the spirit ever anew, ability to read the signs of times and respond accordingly.

3.2 Reconciliation: Becoming Ambassadors of Christ

“We are ambassadors of Christ, since God is making his appeal through us; we entreat you on behalf of Christ, be reconciled to God” (2 Cor 5:20). Today's war-torn world is in a great need of reconciliation. Jesus in his high priestly prayer expresses his desire that all might become one as he and the Father are one (Jn 17:11). In the Old Testament, we have several stories of reconciliation such as Jacob and Esau, Joseph and his brothers, David and Saul, Jonathan the reconciler, Moses standing in the breach and reconciling people with God, etc. In the New Testament, besides the classic texts describing the horizontal reconciliation in the Gospel of Matthew (5:23-24; 18:15-17), Pauline corpus is rich with the theology of reconciliation. The Greek verb *katallasso/katallage* refer to the end of hostility and beginning of friendship.

Reconciliation is already achieved by Jesus Christ through his salvific death on the Cross (Rom 5:10). He has broken down the diving wall separating us from God and from each other (Eph 2:14). In him, there is “no longer Jew or Greek, there is no longer slave or free, there is no longer male and female” (Gal 3:28). From our side, we need to be first receivers of the divine friendship and in turn become his ambassadors extending that friendship to others. St. Paul had a powerful experience of the mercy of Jesus Christ, which transformed his life from being a bitter enemy of Jesus Christ to becoming his intimate friend. He was so much taken up by the self-emptying love of Jesus Christ on the cross that he realized deep within that his

life now was no longer his, but it belonged to Jesus Christ who loved him and gave himself for him (Gal 2:20). St. Paul describes this life-transforming experience with the metaphor of “a new creation.” Like St. Paul, we are called to experience the fullness of reconciliation with God and become a new creation. After being fully reconciled, we become ambassadors of Christ and engage ourselves wholeheartedly in the ministry of reconciliation.

CONCLUSION

Roots and fruits are intimately connected. For fruitful ministry, we, the Church leaders, need to be deeply rooted and grounded in Jesus Christ and his HR values of Holiness and Hospitality, and Repentance and Reconciliation. Like Isaiah, we, are invited to come in the presence of the Lord, get purified, and accept the mission of God eagerly. Like diligent Abraham and discerning Mary of Bethany, we are called to serve God and his people. Following the model of the Ninevites, we have to begin the grassroots movement of repentance. Finally, like St. Paul, a model reconciled reconciler, we need to deeply experience reconciling love of the Lord, and in turn become ambassadors of Christ.

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Dr. Edwin RODRIGUES SJ
<edwinrods@gmail.com>